

IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILL IN EDUCATION AND METHODS OF PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING PROGRAM

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Abstract: Pedagogical excellence in education is an approach to making higher education accessible and reasonable to all. Provision of orientation, appropriate materials, and computer equipment is essential for all teaching and learning systems. The level of education in the twentieth century will be higher than it was in the twentieth century because of these changes and expansions. Conditions are created to prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century and to succeed in the future.

Keywords: Pedagogy, pedagogical methods, modern educational program, teaching technology in education, quality of education, pedagogical skill, teacher potential.

Introduction

Teachers need to incorporate technology into their classrooms. The future educational environment requires teachers to acquire general and specialized knowledge and skills. If the pedagogical approaches in the educational system remain relevant and successful, there will be several changes in education. It is necessary to introduce innovative approaches to pedagogical activities and skills education by improving infrastructure, improving English language proficiency, and expanding online content knowledge and imagination. In the field of education, it is necessary to eliminate the shortage of pedagogic personnel, increase the motivation of teachers, increase awareness of existing pedagogical methods, and strengthen departmental coordination. Helping to overcome barriers has a significant impact on the technology that occurs in the teaching process at all stages of schooling. Thus, it made teaching easier and learning more interesting. Helping teachers improve their professional skills and meet the diverse needs of all types of students, having access to technology in the Republic of Uzbekistan will help ensure access to education for all. In this context, the impact of technology on teaching and learning is enormous. To teach today's students, teachers must recognize the importance of integrating technology and use a variety of methods and tools in pedagogy. The introduction of new and modern technologies into the system of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is being consistently continued. Education affects every

element of human life. Nowadays, it is difficult to imagine the education system without technology. As a result of this development and growth, the educational standards of the twenty-first century will exceed them. Technology-enabled learning in the classroom is critical to preparing students for the technologically advanced curriculum of the 21st century and setting them up for success as we pave the way for future endeavors. In order to survive and succeed in the future educational environment, teachers must learn new pedagogical methods and new general and specialized information. The skill of teachers is the effective use of technology in the classroom. In the educational system, it is called pedagogical competence. Qualified teachers of technological pedagogy should acquire this knowledge. Therefore, the program of using modern technologies in the educational system creates a more convenient and effective opportunity for students to acquire knowledge. Three pillars of pedagogy in educational content, pedagogy and technology. In addition to modern computers, internet, digital video and projectors in the educational system, technologies such as books and blackboards can be used every day. Specializes in the study and application of pedagogy. there are educational theories, methods and procedures. As for the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, pedagogues use various methods to increase the interest and attention of students. So far boring lectures have been cut short. Students can now watch videos or search for interesting information on the Internet. Such classes retain 60% of the subject in the student's memory, and 20% when working independently. Today, most of the industries are working on the basis of technology. We all know that innovation is at the heart of the development of every society. Innovation helps to improve the overall growth and quality of any process, product, service or implemented idea. According to him, inventions in every human society have different forms and levels and spread at different levels. Innovative methods of the educational and training process become more relevant, interesting and valuable through the use of various technologies, which can be explained by the methodology. Stakeholders in the education system should keep them updated. New methods based on innovative pedagogical ideas and approaches should be used to implement knowledge, skills and competencies in education. Moving away from memory and developing more skill-based knowledge has resulted in new pedagogical approaches. A combination of subject matter expertise, teaching and learning methods, and technological pedagogy of an instructional design environment that fosters creativity among teachers and fosters innovation among students. Teachers can attract students' attention and through pedagogy.

By allowing students to remember all the ideas presented, teaching methods that teach theoretical concepts help students improve their memorization skills. In the case of innovative learning students, they need to remember all the subject concepts available. Innovative pedagogy in higher education requires engaging classroom experiences as well as respectful relationships between teachers and students. Helping students build on existing knowledge and skills, developing and designing, and addressing the goal of providing curricula for teachers that are meaningful and relevant to students' needs and cultures. Innovative pedagogical skills help students to make teaching more attractive by developing new ways of teaching teachers and help them achieve their goals. In addition, various innovative pedagogical strategies create a solid foundation for professional development and ensure unity and teamwork among students. "The first step in educating students is to provide and depend on teachers to be innovators." Teachers with a passion for learning are constantly coming up with innovative ways to teach their students new things. All teachers have a unique teaching style based on their belief in their role in education and must ensure that the learning process is meaningful. Some prefer the efficiency of a didactic approach, where content is delivered through lectures or other written materials. Others may take a student-centered approach, where content is delivered through lectures or other means. Others may still use a student-centered approach that uses inquiry-based activities, while others may prefer a collaborative environment where students interact with each other and the teacher reflects. As part of our series on pedagogy, we're taking a deep dive into the definition of pedagogy and what it means. Teachers often talk about their pedagogical approach. Pedagogy is simply defined as the method and practice of improving the quality of education. It includes evaluation of teaching methods, teaching theory and feedback. When people talk about pedagogy, they mean the way teachers deliver curriculum content to the classroom. When planning a lesson, the teacher considers different ways of conveying the content. The decision is based on their educational preferences, experience and the context in which they teach. Pedagogy is often described as the act of teaching. The pedagogy adopted by teachers shapes their actions, thinking and other teachings. In education, learning theory-based strategies focus on understanding student understanding and needs based on individual student backgrounds and interests. Its goals may include the development of liberal education (the general development of human potential) to the narrower features of vocational education (the imparting and acquisition of specific skills). Traditional Western

pedagogy sees the teacher as the possessor of knowledge and the student as the recipient of his knowledge, but pedagogical theories increasingly describe the student as the mediator and the teacher as the facilitator. Pedagogical management: Pedagogical management is a specific type of activity of all subjects of the educational process. It is intended to use methods of goals and forms to support its operation and development as a pedagogical system. According to research, pedagogical management is inextricably linked with certain effects and is necessary for them. High implementation of the target criteria of the educational process: keeping within the established limits (indicators) or moving to a new state (development). According to the author, this type of management is aimed at raising the educational process to a higher level. Optimizing the essence of management in the educational system provides the following conditions for its solution: Planning complex tasks in education. Specification of the components of the educational process according to the selected model in education. Comparative evaluation of different methods of the educational process in terms of suitability for the situation. In general, language teaching and learning has always been open to constant change. With the shift from a descriptive to a critical perspective on language, new approaches to teaching have emerged and social practices have emerged that characterize language learning and similar activities. These approaches are a transition to a more revolutionary critical direction of critical pedagogy. Due to the fact that careful and analytical learning relies on memory, there is a need to conduct creative pedagogical practice among students. The current concentration of students who do not get good grades is understanding the subjects. Cooperation is also weak due to team spirit and competition, which is superior to cooperation. Attention should be paid to the individual character of the student, these requirements are based on interest and intelligence. Rather than relying on teachers, more emphasis should be placed on self-learning. As a result, the focus is on changing innovative pedagogical strategies by introducing innovative skills such as creativity, critical thinking, reasoning, communication, problem solving, collaboration skills and other skills among students. necessary, all these are important in the current situation. However, the successful integration of technology and pedagogy offers many advantages. In order to transform students into productive citizens, teachers must share their knowledge with them. It is necessary to eliminate obstacles in front of students, to strengthen their pedagogical talent. It is important to determine the type of education that is available in the higher education system and that meets the needs of teachers.

In higher education, teachers' perceptions, practices, and readiness for change have the greatest impact. In teacher training programs, it is necessary to take into account the previous knowledge and educational experience of teachers, to listen to their specific needs and requirements for teaching, and to create conditions. Requirements may vary depending on length of experience, confidence in teaching role. Mastery of study in the educational program, etc. In addition, creating the conditions for effective professional development programs is a difficult but necessary task for higher education. In the educational institutions that were previously reviewed and discussed in this article. Educational limitations in collecting personal and academic data about participants for further quantitative analysis, including the types of courses they took and the teaching experience of the research department, informed their perceptions of the education they received. reveals the secret to lum.

Conclusion

This may be an important focus and provides meaningful information for future research. Future work should also consider self and peer evaluation. It is also important to provide empirical insight and understanding of the conceptual frameworks and purposes of curriculum and curriculum models developed by learning centers and curriculum models that differ from teaching or academic structures in higher education institutions, and it is important to delve deeper into the evidence. On the other hand, it should also include qualitative data of monitoring of established dynamics. In education, it is necessary to organize discussions between participants during training sessions. A change in the methodology of an action research or laboratory intervention may be useful to track these teachers' future moments. This will strengthen the process of professional development of the pedagogue. The results of the learned knowledge are always strongly contextualized by the students' exchange of knowledge with each other in organizing discussions in the exchange of ideas.

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